

MIXED FORMULATION WITH STRESSES IN H-DIV SPACE FOR LARGE STRAINS

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Summary

A mixed formulation for large strain-elasticity is presented. The paper extends previous developments for small strain [1,2]. In this contribution, we approximate stresses in H-div space, with displacements, stretches and rotations in L2 spaces. The implementation uses hierarchical approximation bases of arbitrary order. The work is supplemented with a solution scheme that exploits the sparsity of the tangent matrix by using a block Schur-complement solver. Two formulations are briefly described: (1) total Lagrangian and (2) updated Lagrangian formulation for mixed elements and show that solutions are equivalent. The paper will present numerical examples that demonstrate the accuracy of the implementation. The work was implemented in MoFEM (<http://mofem.eng.gla.ac.uk>) [3].

Key Words: *Mixed formulation; H-div; Large deformations; nearly incompressible; polyconvex*

Introduction

A family of mixed finite elements, with stresses approximated in h-div space, has been developed over the past few decades. The formulation of these elements promises optimal convergence for all the approximated variables, i.e. the error reduces at a rate equal to the order of the polynomial approximation field. Weakly enforced symmetry, i.e. where conservation of angular momentum and linear momentum is enforced in a strong integral sense is a particularly attractive feature. This family of elements is characterised by kinematic natural boundary conditions and static essential boundary conditions. Moreover, the displacement field is approximated in L2 space. However, these elements were only developed for linear elastic problems. Here we show a successful mixed element formulation for nearly incompressible materials subjected to large strains.

Furthermore, the lower regularity of the displacement field, i.e. derivatives are not needed and so displacements can be in L2 space (non-conforming elements) will enable us to have material displacements which are caused by plastic flow, thereby providing an opportunity to unify the theory for plasticity and configuration (Eshelbian) mechanics. However, this will form the basis of future work, which will build on the large strain framework described in this paper.

Element formulation*Kinematics*

The spatial gradient of deformation is decomposed as follows

$$h_{iJ} = (\Delta r_{i\alpha} \Delta u_{\alpha\beta}) h_{\beta J}^{\mathcal{I}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{h}^{\mathcal{I}}$ is the spatial gradient of deformation at the intermediate configuration, $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ is finite increment of the spatial stretch tensor and $\Delta \mathbf{r}$ is the increment of spatial rotation. An intermediate configuration is introduced for generality, that enables a total-Lagrangian formulation when $\mathbf{h}^{\mathcal{I}}$ is fixed, and an updated-Lagrangian when $\mathbf{h}^{\mathcal{I}}$ follows the deformation. In this paper for simplicity we use cartesian coordinate system. Indices in large latin letters $(\cdot)_{IJ}$ indicate tensor coefficients in the reference material configuration, small Latin letters $(\cdot)_{ij}$ indicate tensor coefficients in the current spatial configuration, and greek letters $(\cdot)_{\alpha\beta}$ indicate tensor coefficients in the intermediate configuration.

The stretch tensor $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ is symmetric, whereas the rotation $\Delta \mathbf{r}$ is orthonormal and can be expressed using an exponential map, as follows

$$\Delta \mathbf{r} = e^{\mathbf{A}} = \exp(\mathbf{A}), \quad \omega = \|\boldsymbol{\omega}\|, \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = \frac{\boldsymbol{\omega}}{\omega}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the Levi-Civita tensor and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is a pseudovector representing the axis of rotation. In this formulation, the axis of rotation is approximated on the mesh.

Consistency

With the above decomposition at hand, starting with the consistency equation between the gradient of deformation and the gradient of displacement, we get

$$(\delta P_{i\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta r_{i\alpha} \Delta u_{\alpha\beta} - \delta_{i\beta})_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} - \left(\delta P_{i\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \frac{\partial \Delta w_i}{\partial y_\beta} \right)_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where Δw_i displacements in the intermediate configuration and first Piola stress $P_{i\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}}$ in intermediate configuration is

$$P_{i\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}} = \frac{1}{J^{\mathcal{J}}} h_{\alpha J}^{\mathcal{J}} \delta P_{iJ}. \quad (4)$$

where P_{iJ} is stress in reference configuration and $J^{\mathcal{J}} = \det(\mathbf{h}^{\mathcal{J}})$, y_β are coordinates in intermediate configuration. Applying differentiation by parts to the first term in square brackets we get

$$(\delta P_{i\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta r_{i\alpha} \Delta u_{\alpha\beta} - \delta_{i\beta})_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} + (\delta P_{i\beta, \beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta w_i)_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} - (n_\beta^{\mathcal{J}} \delta P_{i\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta \bar{w}_i)_{\partial \Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Note that kinematic constraints are enforced in a weak sense, i.e. constraints on the displacement field are natural boundary conditions.

Physical equation

The physical equations are enforced in an integral, strong sense as follows

$$(\delta u_{\alpha\beta}, \Delta r_{i\alpha} P_{i\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}} - \frac{1}{J^{\mathcal{J}}} h_{\beta J}^{\mathcal{J}} \hat{P}_{\alpha J} (\Delta u_{\alpha\beta} h_{\beta J}^{\mathcal{J}}))_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \quad (6)$$

It should be noted that the above equation is tested (i.e. weighted) by the variation of the stretch tensor.

Angular momentum equation

The conservation of linear momentum is enforced (weakly) in the strong integral sense as follows

$$(\varepsilon_{ij\gamma} \delta \omega_\gamma, P_{i\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}} \Delta h_{j\alpha})_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Linear momentum equation

Finally, the linear conservation equation is enforced as follow

$$(\delta w_i, P_{i\alpha, \alpha}^{\mathcal{J}} - b_i)_{\Omega_t^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0, \quad (8)$$

where b_i are coefficients of body force vector field.

Element equations

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\delta P_{i\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta r_{i\alpha} \Delta u_{\alpha\beta} - \delta_{i\beta})_{\Omega_i^{\mathcal{J}}} + (\delta P_{i\beta,\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta w_i)_{\Omega_i^{\mathcal{J}}} - (n_{\beta}^{\mathcal{J}} \delta P_{i\beta}^{\mathcal{J}}, \Delta \bar{w}_i)_{\partial\Omega_i^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \\ (\delta u_{\alpha\beta}, \Delta r_{i\alpha} (P_{i\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}} - \frac{1}{J_{\mathcal{J}}} h_{\beta J}^{\mathcal{J}} \hat{P}_{iJ}(\mathbf{h})))_{\Omega_i^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \\ (\varepsilon_{ij\gamma} \Delta h_{j\alpha} \delta \omega_{\gamma}, P_{i\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}})_{\Omega_i^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0 \\ (\delta w_i, P_{i\alpha,\alpha}^{\mathcal{J}})_{\Omega_i^{\mathcal{J}}} = 0. \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

Approximation Spaces

With the above equations at hand, the approximation spaces are chosen as follows

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \delta \mathbf{P} \in \mathbf{V}_0^h(\mathcal{K}) \subset H_0^{\text{div}}(\mathcal{B}_0^h) := \{\delta \mathbf{P} \in H_0^{\text{div}}(\mathcal{B}_0^h) : N_j \delta P_{ij} = 0 \text{ on } \partial\mathcal{B}_0^{h,\sigma}\} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{P}} + \mathbf{P} \in \mathbf{V}^h(\mathcal{K}) \subset H^{\text{div}}(\mathcal{B}_0^h) := \{\tilde{\mathbf{P}} + \mathbf{P} \in H^{\text{div}}(\mathcal{B}_0^h) : N_j \delta P_{ij} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} \text{ on } \partial\mathcal{B}_0^{h,\sigma}\} \\ \mathbf{w}, \delta \mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{P}^{k-1}(\mathcal{K}) \subset L^2(\mathcal{B}_0^h) \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}, \delta \boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathcal{P}^k(\mathcal{K}) \subset L^2(\mathcal{B}_0^h) \\ \mathbf{u}, \delta \mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{S}^h \subset \mathbf{S}^{k+1} := \{u_{ij} \in \mathcal{P}^{k+1}(\mathcal{K}) \subset L^2(\mathcal{B}_0^h) : u_{ij} = u_{ij}^T\} \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{K} are non-overlapping tetrahedra covering \mathcal{B}_0^h , and $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathcal{K})$ is the space of polynomials of degree k . H^{div} indicates an H-div conforming space, i.e. vectorial approximation space for which the normal component on element faces is continuous. In this paper, finite element space for stress, after [1], is defined as follows

$$\mathbf{V}(\mathcal{K}) = \mathcal{P}^k(\mathcal{K}) + \text{curl}((\text{curl} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k(\mathcal{K})) \mathbf{b}_K) \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{b}_K is "matrix bubble", and $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^k(\mathcal{K})$ is an antisymmetric matrix of homogenous polynomials of degree k . This space can be considered as an extension of the Brezzi-Douglas-Marini element using a bubble in H-div space. Note that, as a consequence of the properties of the matrix bubble (see details in [1]), the space added to $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathcal{K})$ is a space of "normal bubbles", in the sense that they have zero normal stress components. Moreover, one can note that the divergence of the bubble in the volume is zero.

Linearised system of equations

Linearising the element equations (9), and applying finite element discretisation (10), the system of equations takes the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \overline{\mathbf{P}\mathbf{u}} & \overline{\mathbf{P}\boldsymbol{\omega}} & \overline{\mathbf{P}\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \overline{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}} & \overline{\mathbf{B}\boldsymbol{\omega}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \overline{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{P}} & \overline{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B}} & \overline{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}} & \overline{\mathbf{u}\boldsymbol{\omega}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}\mathbf{P}} & \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}\mathbf{B}} & \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}\mathbf{u}} & \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}\boldsymbol{\omega}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \overline{\mathbf{w}\mathbf{P}} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta \overline{\mathbf{P}} \\ \delta \overline{\mathbf{B}} \\ \delta \overline{\mathbf{u}} \\ \delta \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \\ \delta \overline{\mathbf{w}} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \overline{\mathbf{r}_P} \\ \overline{\mathbf{r}_B} \\ \overline{\mathbf{r}_u} \\ \overline{\mathbf{r}_\omega} \\ \overline{\mathbf{r}_w} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where $\delta \overline{\mathbf{P}}$, $\delta \overline{\mathbf{B}}$, $\delta \overline{\mathbf{u}}$, $\delta \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$, $\delta \overline{\mathbf{w}}$ are degrees of freedom for, stresses, bubble of stresses, stretches, axis of rotations and displacements, respectively. To solve this system of equations, one can apply the process of hybridisation, i.e. introduce another displacement field on the skeleton and "break" the H-div space for stresses. This will lead to a Discontinuous Petrov-Galerkin (DPG) formulation. However, since MoFEM [3] has H-div spaces available, it is possible to use the Schur complement, to eliminate fields one by one, starting from stretches, and then bubbles, to solve the system of equations effectively.

Numerical example

In this section, after [4], we analyse Cook type cantilever problem, with a polyconvex, nearly incompressible Mooney-Rivlin material defined as

$$W_q(\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{h}, j) = \alpha_q (\mathbf{h} : \mathbf{h})^2 + \beta_q (\mathbf{y} : \mathbf{y})^2 + f_q(j) \quad (13)$$

Figure 1: From the left; Cauchy stress σ_{xx} distribution, σ_{xx} on cut (to compare see [4]), displacement u_x (to compare see [4]).

where \mathbf{y} is cofactor $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{h}^{-\mathbf{T}}$, j is Jacobian of \mathbf{h} , and f is defined as follows

$$f_q(j) = -24\beta \ln(j) - 12\alpha \ln(j) + \frac{\lambda}{2\varepsilon^2}(j^\varepsilon + j^{-\varepsilon}) \quad (14)$$

Results are presented on figure 1. The model has 1,575,600 DOFs; stresses and rotations are approximated with 3rd order polynomials, and displacements 2nd order. The DOFs for stretches and bubble functions were solved using the Schur complement, one-by-one at element level.

The geometrical nonlinearities were linearised analytically, and the physical relation, as a function of stretches, is linearised using automatic differentiation with ADOL-C, starting from the strain energy function.

Conclusions

The proposed finite element formulation has excellent potential. It enables separation of nonlinearities that allows for robust solution schemes, good quality solution of stresses, and overall low-regularity. This will enable the unification of configurational mechanics and plasticity in the future.

References

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